

MULTIPASS: IoT Scheduling over a Multilayer NTN Architecture

Mohammad Afhamisis¹ and Maria Rita Palattella¹

¹ENVISION, Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST),
Rue de Brill, Sanem, 4422, Luxembourg.

Contributing authors: mohammad.afhamisis@list.lu;
mariarita.palattella@list.lu;

Abstract

The 6G vision promotes the convergence of terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) to enable seamless Internet of Things (IoT) connectivity, particularly in remote and infrastructure-limited regions. However, direct satellite-IoT communication remains constrained by the low transmission power of IoT devices, intermittent satellite visibility, Doppler-induced signal distortion, and high collision probability, due to the large number of IoT devices, within the satellite coverage. To address these challenges, this work investigates a three-layer IoT-NTN architecture that introduces an intermediate layer composed of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). The latter act as relay, and they forward the data collected data from the IoT devices to Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites through a data collection mechanism, mitigating Doppler effects and improving link reliability. Building on this architecture, we propose MULTIPASS, a novel scheduling method designed to coordinate packet transmissions across terrestrial, aerial, and satellite layers under different UAV flight scenarios, to avoid packet collisions, and thus, saving energy, while improving efficiency. Several UAV flight scenarios are proposed, namely Sequential (S), Adjacent (A), and Direct Relay (D) modes, differing in their data collection timing and satellite visibility coordination. Simulation results, considering LoRaWAN technology, and sequential fly mode, show that MULTIPASS achieves up to 6 times higher data collection than direct satellite communications, and 20 times greater energy efficiency than regular periodic (Aloha-based) transmission, while significantly reducing packet collisions.

Keywords: IoT, UAV, Satellite, 3D Architecture, Scheduling Algorithm

1 Introduction

NTNs have become a fundamental element in the evolution of next-generation mobile communication systems, particularly within the 3GPP’s standardization efforts from Release 17 [1] onward, where NTN are formally integrated into the 5G system architecture as a step toward 6G [2, 3]. NTN encompass satellite systems—including Geostationary (GEO), Medium Earth (MEO), and LEO constellations—as well as high-altitude platforms and airborne relays such as UAVs. Their integration with terrestrial infrastructures is designed to extend connectivity to regions beyond the reach of ground networks and to ensure service continuity under dynamic or harsh conditions. Within this broader vision, NTN are also recognized as an enabling technology for large-scale IoT deployments, where device density, mobility, and energy constraints challenge conventional communication architectures.

Among the technologies driving massive IoT connectivity, Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWANs) provide long-range and low-data-rate communication for battery-operated End Devices (EDs). Long Range (LoRa) and its associated Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol, LoRaWAN [4], have gained significant adoption due to their low power consumption, spread-spectrum modulation, and operation in the unlicensed ISM band. LoRaWAN’s decentralized design allows scalable deployments with minimal infrastructure, but its use of a pure ALOHA channel access mechanism inherently limits channel efficiency and reliability under increased traffic load or asynchronous transmissions. This limitation becomes particularly critical when LoRaWAN is extended toward non-terrestrial links, where propagation delay and visibility constraints further amplify collisions and reduce packet delivery ratio (PDR).

Recent work has explored direct LoRaWAN-based communication between terrestrial EDs and LEO satellites, commonly referred to as IoT-LEO systems [5–8]. These studies have demonstrated the feasibility of establishing LoRa uplinks to LEO satellites, leveraging the modulation’s robustness to support long-distance transmissions. However, the LEO environment introduces additional physical (PHY) layer challenges: high orbital velocities produce large and rapidly varying Doppler shifts, leading to frequency offsets and symbol misalignment that degrade demodulation accuracy [9–11]. Moreover, each satellite provides only short visibility windows over a given ground region, limiting continuous connectivity and making periodic uplinks inefficient. Consequently, while direct IoT-LEO links are technically viable, their reliability remains bounded by Doppler sensitivity and orbital intermittency.

Complementary to this, the integration of LoRa networks with UAVs—forming IoT-UAV systems—has emerged as a flexible solution for enhancing connectivity and data collection efficiency [12–15]. UAVs equipped with LoRa gateways can dynamically reposition to collect data from distributed ground EDs, extending network coverage without introducing significant additional latency. Unlike LEO satellites, UAVs operate at relatively low speeds and altitudes, where Doppler shifts are minimal (typically a few hundred hertz in sub-GHz bands) and have negligible impact on LoRa demodulation [15, 16]. Experimental results confirm that even at UAV speeds approaching 95 km/h, LoRa transmissions with high spreading factors (SFs) maintain

robust link performance. Despite these advantages, current IoT-UAV implementations are mostly limited to localized scenarios and remain disconnected from satellite backhaul infrastructures.

Previous studies have focused either on **IoT-LEO** satellite communication or **IoT-UAV** paradigms systems. This motivates the design of an integrated **IoT-UAV-LEO** architecture that combines terrestrial EDs, mobile UAV gateways, and satellites within a unified 3D NTN framework. Such a multilayer architecture can exploit UAV mobility for asynchronous data collection and align uplinks with satellite visibility windows to overcome the limited temporal availability of LEO links. By coupling terrestrial LoRa transmissions with aerial and orbital scheduling, it becomes possible to mitigate Doppler effects, reduce redundant channel access inherent to pure ALOHA, and increase end-to-end reliability.

However, most existing research on hybrid NTNs [17–19] and UAV-assisted IoT networks [13, 20–23] lacks a unified scheduling framework that jointly governs packet transmissions across terrestrial, aerial, and satellite segments. Current approaches typically treat LoRa data collection, UAV gateway, and satellite forwarding as independent processes, without explicitly synchronizing data flows in time and space across the 3 layers of the 3D network infrastructure. This results in inefficient channel utilization, lower reliability, and suboptimal energy performance.

To address this limitation [24], we propose **MULTIPASS**, a multilayer packet scheduling technique explicitly designed for 3D NTNs integrating IoT, UAV, and LEO satellite segments. **MULTIPASS** introduces cross-layer coordination that synchronizes LoRa transmissions from EDs with UAV trajectories and aligns buffered data with predicted satellite pass times. By leveraging UAV mobility and adaptive timing control, **MULTIPASS** reduces collisions caused by LoRa’s pure ALOHA behavior, minimizes energy consumption, and enhances data delivery reliability across the full communication chain. Simulation results using real Two-Line Element (TLE) satellite data and Software-in-the-Loop (SITL)-based UAV mobility models demonstrate that **MULTIPASS** achieves substantial gains in packet delivery ratio, latency, and energy efficiency compared with conventional periodic or unscheduled LoRaWAN uplinks.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methodologies used for modeling the 3D NTN environment and the corresponding simulation setup. Section 3 presents the proposed 3D NTN system architecture and its functional components. Section 4 details the **MULTIPASS** scheduling algorithm and its cross-layer coordination logic. Section 5 describes the simulation framework, experimental setup, and evaluation methodology, followed by performance analysis and comparative results. Finally, Section 5.3.2 concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

2 Methods

This study introduces **MULTIPASS**, a novel scheduling strategy for data collection in multilayer satellite-enabled IoT systems through an integrated **3D architecture** composed of ground EDs, UAVs acting as mobile gateways, and LEO satellites. The

inclusion of UAVs enhances the connectivity and reliability of IoT-LEO communication by providing flexible and adaptive intermediate EDs for data aggregation.

The methodology begins by identifying the main **constraints** within each layer of the system:

- **IoT layer:** limited energy resources and random access communication inherent to LoRa’s ALOHA-based medium access.
- **UAV layer:** restricted flight duration and trajectory planning challenges affecting link availability and coverage.
- **LEO layer:** intermittent visibility windows and dynamic coverage footprints caused by orbital motion.

Based on these constraints, a set of **system requirements** is defined to overcome operational limitations under realistic conditions. The proposed framework integrates **TLE** data for accurate satellite orbit modeling and **UAV trajectory planning** for optimized spatio-temporal coverage and data retrieval. The resulting scheduling mechanism plans IoT transmissions, and considers UAV relay operations, and satellite passes to ensure energy-efficient and reliable data collection.

A **mathematical formulation** of the scheduling problem is developed to formally represent system constraints and optimization objectives, serving as the basis for the design of the MULTIPASS algorithm.

The proposed approach is validated in a **simulation environment** that emulates realistic spatio-temporal behaviors, including ED distributions, UAV flight paths, and satellite trajectories derived from TLE data. The performance evaluation compares three main test setups: **SIL** (Scheduled IoT-LEO), **PIUL** (Periodical IoT-UAV-LEO), and the proposed **SIUL** (Scheduled IoT-UAV-LEO) method.

Key simulation parameters include the number of EDs, UAV flights, and satellites visibilities. The system performance is assessed using metrics such as PDR and number of packets collected (C).

3 Network Architecture and Flight modes

As shown in Figure. 1, the proposed network architecture is built around a three-tier communication system comprising IoT EDs on the ground, UAVs functioning as mobile gateways, and LEO satellites serving as the upper-layer relay infrastructure. Ground EDs, primarily based on LoRaWAN, are deployed across spatially distributed environments to collect and periodically transmit data according to different application requirements. These EDs, designed for low power consumption, transmit data packets to overhead UAVs when within communication range. Each UAV is equipped with a LoRaWAN-compatible gateway mounted onboard, which enables data acquisition from multiple EDs during flight operations. As the UAVs follow predetermined or adaptive flight paths over the deployment area, they collect data using short-range, energy-efficient wireless links without requiring the ground EDs to adjust transmission power or perform long-range communication like direct to LEO satellite communications.

Fig. 1 Multilayer NTN (IoT-UAV-LEO) architecture vs Direct IoT-LEO

The UAVs implement a data collection mechanism, buffering received packets and temporarily holding them until satellite connectivity becomes available. The UAV processes incoming packets locally, allowing decoding, deduplication, and proper queuing prior to uplink. This module ensures that packets can be managed effectively without introducing heavy computational or memory demands, enabling real-time responsiveness and autonomous operation. LEO satellites, orbiting the Earth several times a day, establish periodic contact windows with UAVs during their passes. When a UAV enters one of these visibility intervals, buffered data is uploaded to the satellite using suitable uplink protocols and frequencies, completing the end-to-end delivery chain from ED to satellite relay.

A core limitation of direct IoT-to-LEO communication is addressed in this architecture. In the absence of a UAV layer, LoRa-based EDs would be required to transmit directly to satellite gateways, a process that imposes significant energy overhead, demands complex antenna orientation, and suffers from low availability due to short satellite visibility periods and beam coverage gaps. By contrast, introducing UAVs as mid-tier gateways enhances data availability, lowers the transmission burden on ground EDs, and enables more frequent data collection cycles.

However, the insertion of UAVs introduces new challenges, particularly related to timing, coordination, and data reliability. Packet collisions can occur if multiple EDs transmit simultaneously within a UAV's coverage zone, especially in dense deployments or overlapping flight paths. Additionally, UAV flight durations are constrained by battery capacity and payload weight, limiting the time available for data collection and necessitating efficient scheduling to prevent packet drops. To address these issues, the architecture requires a dedicated packet scheduling mechanism that aligns data transmissions from ground EDs with UAV availability while minimizing contention. These mechanisms ensure that EDs transmit only when necessary, avoiding redundant attempts and reducing the probability of channel congestion.

We propose the following three modes for UAV flights and data collections, described in Figure. 2:

- **Mode S - S(quential) Flight Mode** - In this mode, the UAV performs multiple flights over the field farm, collecting and decoding data from the EDs during each pass. The data collected is stored onboard the UAV until a LEO satellite becomes visible. Once satellite connectivity is established, the UAV forwards the stored data to the satellite for further processing. This mode is ideal for areas with infrequent satellite visibility, ensuring that all is collected prior to transmission.
- **Mode A - Satellite A(djacent) Mode** - This mode synchronizes UAV flights with the upcoming satellite visibility windows. The UAV starts its flight shortly before the satellite appears in its communication range. After gathering and decoding data from EDs, the UAV forwards the collected data to the satellite immediately after completing the data collection phase. This mode minimizes data storage requirements on the UAV while optimizing the timing of data transfers.
- **Mode D - D(irect) Relay Mode** - In this mode, the UAV operates during periods of simultaneous satellite visibility. As the UAV collects data from EDs, it directly forwards the data to the satellite without intermediate storage. This mode supports near-real-time data relays and is suitable for delay-sensitive applications (e.g., monitoring of forest fire).

Fig. 2 Data collection Modes between the UAV and the LEO satellite.

4 MULTIPASS

The implementation of a 3D network architecture where EDs transmit data to a UAV that subsequently forwards it to a satellite (*Mode S*), necessitates a robust packet scheduling mechanism, to ensure the achievement of the target PDR. The intermittent availability of both the UAV, and the LEO satellite makes this scenario very challenging. In this section, we focus on the access network, and thus on the communication between the EDs on the ground and the flying gateway, mounted on the UAV, independently from the (satellite) backhauling link. The location of the EDs, and the UAV fly pattern play a role in the design of the packet scheduling technique. The UAV could follow a pre-established path (for instance, aiming at inspecting the entire field farm), or an optimal path, aiming at minimizing the fly duration (and thus, the energy

consumption of the UAV), while visiting all the EDs in the field, and maximizing the amount of data collected. As a baseline scenario, we assumed that all the EDs have a fixed location in the field farm, and the UAV follows a pre-established path, independently from the exact location of the EDs, and amount of traffic generated. The proposed MULTIPASS scheduling technique takes into account: (i) the UAV’s trajectory and flight time, which determine its availability at specific locations and time intervals; and (ii) the location of the ED, which defines its visibility window relative to the UAV’s path. In our previous work [5], we proposed a similar transmission priority approach, namely SALSA scheduling algorithm, where EDs communicating directly with LEO satellites (IoT-LEO). In SALSA, we assign higher transmission priority to the EDs that are first in the satellite’s visibility, with the aim of maximizing the available time for data transfer. Therefore, MULTIPASS follows the same policy by giving higher priority to the EDs being earlier in the visibility of a UAV. In MULTIPASS, the trajectory of UAVs are taken into account which can be modified based on the requirements of the mission, but SALSA should follow the satellite visibility based on a fixed satellite orbital trajectory. UAV needs also to follow the satellite’s visibility to upload collected packets to the network, similar to the SALSA. When considering a specific IoT technology, further consideration must be taken. For instance, for LoRa technology, regional transmission constraints, such as duty cycle limitations, must also be accounted for. Even if a ED is within the UAV’s visibility, it cannot transmit if its duty cycle restriction has not been met. Additionally, to prevent packet collisions, the scheduling mechanism avoids two or several EDs transmitting simultaneously, on the same channel and same PHY layer setup (like SF in LoRa). Transmissions occurs in sequence, with each ED waiting for the previous one to finish before initiating its own transmission. Figure 3 illustrated the logic of the scheduling technique.

We model slot scheduling as a constrained optimization problem. For each ED i , let $V_i = [t_i^{\text{start}}, t_i^{\text{end}}]$ denote its visibility window with the UAV. Let A_i denote the airtime required to transmit one packet, computed from the LoRaWAN specification as a function of the SF, payload size, and bandwidth. Our goal is to maximize the PDR while respecting duty-cycle and collision constraints.

$$\text{PDR} = \frac{m}{n} \quad (1)$$

where m and n denote the number of packets *received* and *transmitted*, respectively, subject to the following constraints:

$$t_i^{\text{start}} \leq s_i \leq t_i^{\text{end}} - A_i, \quad \forall i \quad (\text{slot must be within UAV visibility}) \quad (2)$$

$$s_i \geq s_{i-1} + A_{i-1} + g, \quad \forall i \quad (\text{avoid overlap with guard time } g) \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{k \in W_i} A_k \leq \text{DC}_i \cdot |W_i|, \quad \forall i \quad (\text{duty-cycle constraint}) \quad (4)$$

where s_i is the transmission start time assigned to ED i , g is a fixed guard time between slots, and W_i is the duty-cycle regulation window for ED i . If no feasible s_i exists inside V_i , the packet is not scheduled.

Fig. 3 MULTIPASS Scheduling Diagram

EDs are scheduled sequentially according to their visibility order. For example, ED1, which first enters the UAV's visibility, receives the first transmission slot. Device ED2, which also has early visibility, must wait for ED1 to complete its transmission before transmitting, and the same applies for all other EDs up to ED(n). The guard time g accounts for timing uncertainties and potential synchronization errors between EDs and the UAV, preventing unintended overlaps and ensuring robust packet delivery.

Duty cycle limitations are considered in the scheduling. If ED1 attempts a second transmission after its duty cycle reset, it will collide with ED(n)'s ongoing transmission. To solve this, the algorithm shifts ED1's second transmission to occur after ED(n) completes its transmission. Similarly, the transmission slots for ED2 and ED3 are adjusted to prevent conflicts. However, for ED3, shifting the second transmission slot would place it outside the UAV's visibility window, leading to a canceled transmission. The same issue arises with ED($n-1$), where its second transmission would extend beyond UAV visibility, forcing the algorithm to drop the packet. Besides scheduling on the access link, distinct data collection modes can be envisaged on the satellite backhauling, depending on the interaction between UAV flights and satellite visibility.

Although this study focuses on Mode S, MULTIPASS can be adapted for Modes A and D by adding uplink-deadline constraints to the slot allocator. For Mode A, the scheduler biases transmission completion toward upcoming satellite passes to minimize UAV buffer time. For Mode D, transmission deadlines are enforced such that packets are uploaded immediately after collection. Despite Mode S, Modes A and D imply less freedom on fly schedules. Sometimes, satellites are visible during midnight, therefore it would make it difficult for the UAV operators to collect the data.

5 Performance Analysis

In the performance analysis we have assumed that sequential flight mode (*Mode S*) is adopted, since it allows collecting many packets that are temporary stored on the UAV, and can be forwarded, once the LEO satellite is available. Thus, it ensures high PDR, at the price of higher energy consumption for the UAV that must flight several times in sequence. Mode A and Mode D request additional effort in the synchronization between the UAV and the satellite and reduce the amount of time for data collection from the EDs. A detailed analysis of Modes A and D will be considered in future work.

5.1 Simulation Environment

The proposed connectivity solution, and related network architecture, encompassing two NTN elements (UAV and LEO satellite) has been reproduced in a simulated environment, coded in Python. We assumed that EDs distributed across one or multiple farms, transmit data using the LoRa modulation and the LoRaWAN protocol. The tool includes a packet generator, and support two different types of traffic: periodic (following standard LoRa class A Aloha-based communication), and scheduled (when a scheduling technique is implemented, and transmissions are triggered according to the availability of the UAV and/or the satellite). Packets can be classified in 3 different categories: (i) delivered, when the packet is successfully received by (the gateway installed on) the UAV; (ii) collided, when the packet encounters an interference due to simultaneous transmissions (on the same channel, with the same SF); (iii) dropped, when the UAVs is not available (e.g., it moves outside the coverage range, by the time that the packet is transmitted by the EDs, or it is flying in another field, or due to PHY layer limitations - e.g., link budget limitations: the distance between the EDs and the flying UAV exceeds viable communication thresholds).

As described in the pseudo-code of Algorithm 1, the simulator takes in input: EDs' location - D -, UAV trajectory - T - and Uplink Traffic - U -. The ArduPilot's native SITL simulator [25] was used to simulate a Multi-Rotor UAV traveling on a desired mission. Position of the UAV, in terms of latitude, longitude, and altitude is considered at discrete time stamps (every 1sec), to measure the relative distance from the EDs, and thus, to check when they enter the UAV's visibility window. Traffic is classified as overlapping (in case of concurrent transmissions from several EDs, in absence of appropriate scheduling techniques), and not overlapping. The Simulator performs PHY layer checks to identify collided and dropped packets. All the data successfully received, is temporary stored on the UAV, till a LEO satellite will be available for the backhauling (assuming Mode S - Sequential Flight Mode). UAV data collection is managed according to Algorithm 1. The UAV gathers data multiple times per day and stores it ($Data_{UAV}$). As described in Algorithm 2, once the satellite enters its visibility window, denoted as $[S_{s(i)}, S_{e(i)}]$, the UAV initiates data uploads, constrained by available satellite bandwidth. If the accumulated data volume exceeds the available uplink capacity, pending packets are deferred to subsequent satellite passes.

Algorithm 1 IoT–UAV Segment

Require: $\forall D_i \in \mathbb{D}, \forall T_i \in \mathbb{T}, \forall U_i \in \mathbb{U}$ **Ensure:** Data_{UAV}

```
1: for all  $U_i \in \mathbb{U}$  do
2:   if  $T_i$  is active then
3:     if  $U_i$  is non-overlapping with other  $U_j \in \mathbb{U}$  then
4:       if  $\text{SNR} \geq \text{SNR}_{\text{req}}$  then
5:         Store data from  $U_i$  at UAV
6:       else
7:         Drop  $U_i$  ▷ Due to budget link
8:       end if
9:     else ▷ Overlapping in time
10:      if  $SF_i = SF_j$  and  $CH_i = CH_j$  then
11:        Mark  $U_i$  as Collided
12:      else
13:        if  $\text{SNR} \geq \text{SNR}_{\text{req}}$  then
14:          Store data from  $U_i$  at UAV
15:        end if
16:      end if
17:    end if
18:  else
19:    Drop  $U_i$  ▷ UAV unavailable
20:  end if
21: end for
```

Algorithm 2 UAV–LEO Segment

Require: $\Sigma[S_{s(i)}, S_{e(i)}]$ (satellite visibility intervals), $\forall U_i \in \text{Data}_{\text{UAV}}$ **Ensure:** Data_{Sat}

```
1: for all  $U_i \in \text{Data}_{\text{UAV}}$  do
2:   if Satellite is available during  $[S_{s(i)}, S_{e(i)}]$  then
3:     Wait until packet is uploaded
4:     Add  $U_i$  to  $\text{Data}_{\text{Sat}}$ 
5:     Remove  $U_i$  from  $\text{Data}_{\text{UAV}}$ 
6:   else
7:     Wait for the next satellite pass
8:   end if
9: end for
```

5.2 Test Setup

In the simulation, the area of interest—where the UAV operates and the sensors are deployed—was defined as a $2.5 \times 1.5 \text{ km}^2$ region in Echternach, Luxembourg, selected to represent a semi-rural environment characterized by moderate sensor density. A pre-defined UAV trajectory is defined (Figure 4) for inspecting the entire area with flight

Fig. 4 Flight trajectory with $N=100$ EDs spread over the area (Echternach region, Luxembourg - $2.5 \text{ km} \times 1.5 \text{ km}^2$)

duration of 13 minutes with maximum speed of 10 km/h , regardless the specific locations of the EDs. We assumed that UAVs have no memory limits for store-and-forward operation, while they are collecting IoT traffic and forwarding to the Satellites. Within this region, between $N=5$ and $N=100$ EDs were randomly deployed, each configured to operate on the EU868 MHz band using channel 1 and a fixed $SF = 12$. A fixed $SF = 12$ is chosen to represent a worst-case scenario in terms of airtime and potential channel occupancy. Adaptive data rate (ADR) is not applied because it requires precise link budget calculations and the ability for devices to select their SFs dynamically. In the UAV-assisted scenario, gateways are mobile, making ADR impractical, as it is most effective when the gateway position is fixed. This configuration emphasizes long-range, low-bit rate communication and represents a worst-case scenario in terms of airtime consumption and potential channel occupancy. All transmissions adhered to the 1% duty cycle limitation imposed by the regional regulatory framework. The scheduler introduced a guard time of 20 milliseconds at the end of each time slot to prevent potential time synchronization issues, thereby reducing the risk of packet collision and ensuring robust slot separation even under hardware or propagation delays.

Three distinct test scenarios were simulated; PIUL, SIUL, and SIL [5]. In the first, EDs transmitted periodically every 30 minutes without any packet scheduling technique, resulting in potentially colliding and dropping packets. To reduce collision probability, randomness was introduced in the start time of the EDs' transmission. This reproduces the randomness in the join process. The second scenario implemented the proposed MULTIPASS method, where a UAV sequentially collects data from each visible ED based on a deterministic schedule that incorporated guard times and

respected duty cycle constraints. The UAV then stored the packets and forwarded them during subsequent satellite visibility periods. The satellite infrastructure was modeled using ASTROCAST LEO satellite constellation ranging from 1 to 10 satellites at approximately 500 km altitude [26], reflecting realistic visibility windows and pass durations. This comprehensive simulation environment allowed for the comparative evaluation of transmission reliability, latency, and channel utilization efficiency under practical operational constraints. Satellite visibility windows were calculated using orbital parameters obtained from CelesTrack online TLE source [27]. During the satellite visibility window, the UAV uploads the stored packets using a forward link protocol. The simulator assumes a session set-up time of 10 sec, and an upload speed of 80 Kb/s for satellite communication. The duration of the test was 48 hours.

5.3 Results and Discussion

5.3.1 PDR and Data Collection

As illustrated in Figure 5, we evaluated the PDR under three transmission scenarios: PIUL, SIUL, and SIL over 10 independent simulation runs. For both the periodic transmission and MULTIPASS cases, the evaluation was conducted over $F=10$ UAV flight intervals during the test period, reflecting realistic operational conditions with intermittent connectivity between IoT EDs, UAVs, and LEO satellites. As anticipated, both scheduling techniques designed to mitigate packet collisions and drops achieve PDR values of 100%, demonstrating robust and consistent delivery performance during the test. In contrast, the scenario employing periodic transmissions without scheduling yields a markedly degraded PDR, consistently falling below 5% across all UAV passes. This degradation mainly results from the unawareness of EDs about the UAV flight schedule, causing many packets to be transmitted when no UAV is within range, and thus lost. Moreover, even when the UAV becomes visible, the simultaneous unscheduled transmissions from multiple EDs lead to frequent packet collisions, further lowering the PDR. This outcome highlights the adverse impact of uncoordinated transmissions in multi-hop NTN environments, where lead to substantial packet loss. The results confirm that collision-aware scheduling mechanisms are essential not only for ensuring high reliability but also for enabling scalability in dense IoT deployments over 3D architectures.

To further evaluate the impact of introducing an UAV layer, we compared the performance of the MULTIPASS and SALSA scheduling methods to assess the benefits of deploying UAVs between ground-based EDs and LEO satellites. As illustrated in Figure 6, the number of successfully collected packets was recorded for varying network densities of $N=\{5,50,100\}$ EDs. The evaluation considered two different configurations: SALSA was tested with varying numbers of LEO satellites $S=\{1,3,5,10\}$, while MULTIPASS was evaluated using a single satellite to represent a constrained orbital scenario, with varying numbers of UAV flights $F=\{1,3,5,10\}$ throughout the test duration. This figure enables a direct comparison between increasing satellite density in a purely SIL setup (SALSA) and increasing UAV flights in the SIUL configuration (MULTIPASS). Notably, when using $F=10$ UAV flights with a single satellite ($S=1$), MULTIPASS achieves comparable or superior performance relative to SALSA,

Fig. 5 PDR comparison between periodical and scheduled methods over 10 independent simulation runs; error bars represent standard deviation.

even in scenarios with a higher number of satellites and a similar network density of $N=100$ EDs. This demonstrates that augmenting UAV coverage through additional flight intervals can effectively compensate for reduced satellite visibility, maintaining high data collection efficiency. Conversely, when only a single UAV flight is available, SALSA with multiple satellites outperforms MULTIPASS, underscoring the sensitivity of performance to UAV availability. These results confirm that integrating UAVs as mobile store and forward link—when paired with a packet scheduling method like MULTIPASS—offers a viable and scalable alternative to increasing satellite density for regional IoT-NTN deployments.

During the tests, we observed that although the UAV collected many packets from the ground EDs and uploaded them to the satellites, the number of packets actually received by the satellites was lower than those collected by the UAV. As shown in Figure 7, the final UAV flight occurred after the last satellite pass, meaning no satellite was available to receive the transmitted packets. These remaining data would have been forwarded to the next satellite passes, but due to the limited test period, this was not possible.

Additionally, we evaluated the impact of varying UAV-to-LEO upload speeds on data delivery, considering different numbers of LEO satellites $S=\{1,5,10\}$. As shown in Figure 8, for a test configuration with $N=100$ IoT EDs and $F=10$ UAV flights, increasing the upload speed reduces the number of satellites required to achieve reliable data collection. However, decreasing satellite count introduces increased latency in packet delivery and delayed transmission to monitoring centers. The number of collected packets saturates beyond a certain upload rate (500 B/s) due to the limited data volume from a single region. In larger-scale deployments with multiple geographic regions or

Fig. 6 Collected Packets; IoT-UAV-LEO with MULTIPASS vs. IoT-LEO with SALSA

higher ED densities, the required number of satellites would grow proportionally with data throughput demands.

5.3.2 Estimation of Energy Efficiency

After evaluating the reliability in terms of PDR and the number of collected packets, it is also important to analyze the **energy consumption implications** of the two transmission strategies.

Let X denote the unit energy consumed by the ED during a single uplink transmission. If n transmissions are attempted, the total energy expenditure is nX . Out of these attempts, let m denote the number of successful packet deliveries. We define the *energy efficiency* η as the number of successful transmissions per unit energy:

$$\eta = \frac{m}{nX}. \quad (5)$$

Relating η to the PDR from Equation. 1:

$$\text{PDR} = \frac{m}{n} \Rightarrow m = n \cdot \text{PDR}, \quad (6)$$

The efficiency can be rewritten as

$$\eta = \frac{\text{PDR}}{X}. \quad (7)$$

This shows that energy efficiency scales directly with delivery reliability, normalized by the per-transmission cost X .

For the **SIUL transmission strategy**, our results show that $\text{PDR} = 100\%$, so

$$\eta_{\text{SIUL}} = \eta_{\text{max}} = \frac{1}{X}. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 7 Satellite visibility of selected satellites from the ASTROCAST constellation for the UAV flying over the ground EDs vs. UAV's Flights

This highlights that SIUL transmissions not only improve reliability but also maximize the energy payoff per successfully delivered packet, while PIUL strategies waste energy on failed attempts despite producing some successful deliveries through volume.

By contrast, in the **PIUL strategy**, the PDR can be very low (e.g., $< 5\%$), but a *large number of transmissions* still produces some successful deliveries.

To illustrate the difference in performance between periodic and scheduled strategies, we consider a simple example with a periodic interval of 900 seconds over 2 days (172,800 s). The computations for total transmissions and successful deliveries are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Example calculation of transmissions and successful deliveries for PIUL and SIUL strategies

Strategy	Computation	Result
PIUL-10F-1S	Transmissions per ED: $172,800/900$	≈ 192
	Total transmissions (100 EDs): 192×100	19,200
	Successful packets (PDR = 5%): $19,200 \times 0.05$	960
SIUL-10F-1S	Successful packets (PDR = 100%): $1,280 \times 1.00$	1,280

From Table 1, It is clear that even with a low PDR of $\approx 5\%$ for PIUL-10F-1S, the total number of successful deliveries is 960 packets (Table 1, row 3), compared to 1,280 packets for SIUL-10F-1S (Table 1, row 4).

$$\eta_{\text{PIUL}} = \frac{960}{19,200X} = \frac{0.05}{X} \quad \text{vs.} \quad \eta_{\text{SIUL}} = \frac{1,280}{1,280X} = \frac{1}{X}.$$

As reflected in Table 1, SIUL transmissions not only improve reliability but also maximize the energy payoff per successfully delivered packet. In summary, the results confirm that incorporating a UAV layer is essential for bridging IoT and LEO segments, and that a dedicated scheduling technique like MULTIPASS is crucial to ensure reliable and scalable operation across the multilayer architecture.

Fig. 8 Effect of number of satellites, $S=\{1,5,10\}$, and Upload Speed (B/s) on the C , data collection, by Satellites ($F=10, N=100$)

Conclusion

This work presented a multilayer IoT-NTN architecture that integrates terrestrial EDs, UAV-based aerial gateways, and LEO satellites into a unified 3D communication framework. The study was motivated by the inherent limitations of direct IoT-LEO links, where the combination of low transmission power, pure ALOHA channel access, and intermittent satellite visibility restricts link reliability and scalability. To address these constraints, the UAV layer was introduced as an adaptive intermediary that performs asynchronous data collection and temporally aligns packet forwarding with satellite availability.

Building on this architecture, we proposed **MULTIPASS**, a cross-layer scheduling technique designed to coordinate packet transmissions across the terrestrial, aerial, and satellite segments. MULTIPASS leverages UAV mobility to schedule LoRa uplinks, receive collected data, and synchronizes satellite transmissions based on predicted orbital passes. This design effectively mitigates the impact of Doppler variation,

reduces redundant ALOHA-based collisions, and minimizes the energy overhead on ground EDs.

A comprehensive simulation framework was developed to evaluate the proposed system under realistic operational conditions, incorporating real TLE satellite data, SITL UAV mobility, and LoRa physical-layer constraints. Results demonstrated that the integration of UAV relays with predictive scheduling markedly improves data collection efficiency compared to both direct IoT-LEO communication and unscheduled periodic baselines. In particular, MULTIPASS achieved up to 6 times higher data collection performance and a 20 times improvement in energy efficiency, confirming that cross-layer coordination substantially enhances the reliability and sustainability of IoT-NTN systems.

Overall, this work demonstrates that UAV-assisted scheduling provides a scalable and energy-efficient alternative to increasing satellite density for regional IoT connectivity. By bridging the temporal and spatial gaps between terrestrial and orbital segments, the proposed approach establishes a foundation for adaptive, delay-tolerant, and resource-aware communication in future 6G NTN.

Future work will focus on extending the simulator to incorporate optimized UAV flight planning algorithms and to evaluate the architecture in a real-world testbed implementation. Additionally, future investigations will consider a broader range of assumptions, such as possible memory limitations on UAVs for data storage, and more diverse scenarios including different ED distributions, varying traffic priorities, and adaptive scheduling strategies. These enhancements aim to better reflect practical deployment constraints and further validate the robustness of the proposed architecture.

List of Abbreviations

Table 2 List of abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
<i>3GPP</i>	3rd Generation Partnership Project
<i>ADR</i>	Adaptive Data Rate
<i>ED</i>	End Device
<i>GEO</i>	Geostationary Earth Orbit
<i>IoT</i>	Internet of Things
<i>LEO</i>	Low Earth Orbit
<i>LoRa</i>	Long Range
<i>LoRaWAN</i>	Long Range Wide Area Network
<i>MAC</i>	Medium Access Control
<i>MEO</i>	Medium Earth Orbit
<i>MULTIPASS</i>	IoT Scheduling over a Multilayer NTN Architecture
<i>NTN</i>	Non-Terrestrial Network
<i>PDR</i>	Packet Delivery Ratio
<i>PHY</i>	Physical Layer
<i>PIUL</i>	Periodical IoT-UAV-LEO
<i>SALSA</i>	A Scheduling Algorithm for LoRa to LEO Satellites
<i>SF</i>	Spreading Factor
<i>SIL</i>	Scheduled IoT-LEO (SALSA)
<i>SIUL</i>	Scheduled IoT-UAV-LEO (MULTIPASS)
<i>SITL</i>	Software In The Loop
<i>SNR</i>	Signal to Noise Ratio
<i>TLE</i>	Two Line Elements
<i>UAV</i>	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

Declarations

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- **Availability of data and materials** The data and materials used in this study are available upon reasonable request, subject to the intellectual property (IP) protection and data-sharing policies of the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST). Public release, if applicable, will be considered in accordance with institutional guidelines.
- **Authors’ contributions** All authors contributed equally to the conception, design, and writing of this manuscript.

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- **Competing interests** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Figure Title and Legend

This section provides a detailed description of the figures presented in this paper.

Figure 1. Multilayer NTN (IoT-UAV-LEO) architecture vs Direct IoT-LEO This figure compares the proposed multilayer NTN architecture—including IoT

EDs on the ground, UAV layer, and LEO satellites—with a direct IoT-to-LEO configuration. The multilayer approach enhances uplink robustness by introducing UAVs as mobile gateways that address satellite visibility and ED power limitations.

Figure 2. Data collection modes between the UAV and the LEO satellite The diagram illustrates three operational data collection scenarios involving UAVs and LEO satellites under the 3D network architecture.

Figure 3. MULTIPASS Scheduling Architecture This figure presents how MULTIPASS method works, and arranges scheduling timeslots, This method considers priorities based on the location of the ED and UAV Trajectory, and adopts with LoRaWAN regulations.

Figure 4. Flight trajectory with N=100 EDs in Echternach, Luxembourg This figure presents the a custom UAV trajectory over a $2.5 \text{ km} \times 1.5 \text{ km}^2$ area for collecting data from 100 EDs. The trajectory serves as the basis for evaluating scheduling efficiency.

Figure 5. PDR comparison between periodic and scheduled methods A quantitative comparison of PDR for periodic (PIUL) vs. scheduled transmission strategies (SIUL and SIL) for 10 UAV flights and 10 Satellites. MULTIPASS significantly improves PDR by aligning packet transmissions with UAV availability and satellite coverage windows.

Figure 6. Collected packets: IoT-UAV-LEO with MULTIPASS vs IoT-LEO with SIL The figure shows the number of successfully collected packets under MULTIPASS (SIUL) versus SALSA (SIL). It demonstrates their difference for different number of UAV flights $\{1,3,5,10\}$ with 1 Satellite in SIUL and different number of Satellites $\{1,3,5,10\}$ in SIL.

Figure 7. Satellite visibility from ASTROCAST constellation vs UAV flights This figure maps the visibility periods of selected LEO satellites from the ASTROCAST constellation versus the UAV’s flight trajectory. X axis stands for the test duration, and Y axis as name of considered satellites and the UAV.

Figure 8. Effect of Number of satellites on achievable bitrate The graph presents upload speed from UAV to Satellite as a function of the number of satellites deployed $S = \{1, 5, 10\}$ and $F=10$ UAV flights. This figure proves that satellite upload speed is an important factor in dense networks.